

CriticalFires

Interaction between wildfires and Critical Zone dynamics

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Deliverable D3

Report on the harmonization of the CriticalFires modeling suite and related instructions for use

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CriticalFires - RETURN

Deliverable 3

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1 Introduction

In fire-prone ecosystems, vegetation structure and soil carbon dynamics interact in complex ways, with vegetation influencing soil carbon turnover and soil conditions affecting vegetation succession and resilience. Understanding these interactions is essential for assessing ecosystem stability and carbon storage potential [1, 3].

The work presented here combines two models to explore these interactions: the vegetation dynamics model, a modification of the models introduced in [1, 2], focusing on transitions between bare soil, grassland, shrubland, and woodland and includes the response to fire disturbances, and the RothC soil carbon model, which simulates soil organic carbon cycling. A fire propagation model can also be coupled to the main soil-vegetation model discussed here. Together, these models allow us to study how vegetation structure influences soil carbon dynamics and how soil organic carbon content, in turn, affects vegetation stability and resilience against fire disturbances, providing an integrated model of the interplay of fires and the Critical Zone.

2 Vegetation Dynamics Model

The vegetation model adopted here simulates vegetation dynamics in a fire-prone ecosystem at monthly scale, representing the landscape as a grid of cells, each of which contains a mix of bare soil and four different vegetation types: grass, shrub, and woodland composed of seeders (e.g. pines) and resprouters (e.g. holm oaks). Each vegetation type has distinct growth patterns, flammability, and responses to disturbances, which drive transitions between vegetation states over time. This model captures the dynamics of vegetation succession, fire disturbances, and feedback mechanisms that lead to alternative stable states, such as persistent grasslands or resilient woodlands. This model is then coupled

to soil carbon dynamics. All biomass and area variables are expressed in ton (10^3 kg) and hectare (10^4 m²), while time is expressed in years.

2.1 Vegetation Composition and Succession at Annual Scale

First we discuss vegetation dynamics at annual scale, using a simplification of the original model proposed in [1]. The l -th cell of a grid of N cells represents an area of homogeneous climatic and edaphic conditions large enough (e.g., from 20×20 m² to 100×100 m²) to encompass coexistence of multiple vegetation types. Specific combination of grass, shrub, and woodland vegetation types were considered in each cell. The model simulates vegetation succession, with cells evolving from grass to shrub, and from shrub to woodland, according to succession rates represented by the parameters $0 < \beta_{gs} < 1$ (grass to shrub) and $0 < \beta_{sw} < 1$ (shrub to woodland). The succession process at the cell level is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} G^{(l)}(t+1) &= G^{(l)}(t) - \beta_{gs} G^{(l)}(t), \\ S^{(l)}(t+1) &= S^{(l)}(t) + \beta_{gs} G^{(l)}(t) - \beta_{sw} S^{(l)}(t), \\ W^{(l)}(t+1) &= W^{(l)}(t) + \beta_{sw} S^{(l)}(t) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where $G^{(l)}(t)$, $S^{(l)}(t)$, $W^{(l)}(t)$ are the proportions (fractions of cell area) of grass (G), shrubs (S), and trees (woodland, W) within the l -th cell at time t . In this formulation, the time t indicates the year and it is incremented by one year at each step (that is, the successional dynamics has a time step of one year). In the original model [1], a further distinction was made based on a parameter indicating the TSF (Time Since Fire), which determined different values of the succession parameters. Here, since the succession velocity will be made explicitly dependent upon the soil carbon (and nutrient) content and soil moisture, we avoid this complication and keep the values of the transition parameters β independent of the time since last fire. On the other hand, the transition parameters will depend on the available carbon content of the soil and, where appropriate, on soil moisture.

Note that, at each time t and in each cell l , the total area covered is $G^{(l)}(t) + S^{(l)}(t) + W^{(l)}(t) = G^{(l)}(0) + S^{(l)}(0) + W^{(l)}(0) = 1$, i.e., during the time evolution, the proportions (fractions of area covered by the various vegetation types) remain positive and sum to 1 (i.e. the three classes together cover the total area of the cell). Notice, also, that in this extremely simplified formulation the vegetation type “grass” includes small patches of bare soil. This simplified approach will be made more realistic in the monthly-scale model.

2.2 Undisturbed Vegetation Succession at Monthly Scale

For the coupling with soil carbon dynamics, we need to express vegetation dynamics at monthly scale (i.e., the timestep should now become $h = 1/12$ yr and

not a year as in the previous section). However, we keep counting time in units of years.

The transition parameters in the vegetation succession must then be expressed at monthly scale, and their sum over one year must be equal to the corresponding annual value. In the simplest case, and the one adopted here, one can simply assume no seasonal cycle in the succession and assume that the monthly-scale succession parameters are the annual values multiplied by $h = 1/12$ yr.

In extending the description of vegetation succession at monthly scale and couple it with soil carbon dynamics, we need also to modify the original model and include a component of bare soil, as grass takes more than one month to recolonize the burned land, and the distinction between highly-flammable seeder trees (e.g. pines) and low-flammable resprouter broadleaves (e.g. holm oaks), in the spirit of [2]. The succession process at cell level and monthly scale is then expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}
B^{(l)}(t_{n+1}) &= B^{(l)}(t_n) - h \beta_{bg} B^{(l)}(t_n), \\
G^{(l)}(t_{n+1}) &= G^{(l)}(t_n) + h [\beta_{bg} B^{(l)}(t_n) - \beta_{gs} G^{(l)}(t_n)], \\
S^{(l)}(t_{n+1}) &= S^{(l)}(t_n) + h [\beta_{gs} G^{(l)}(t_n) - \beta_{sp} S^{(l)}(t_n) - \beta_{sh} S^{(l)}(t_n)], \\
P^{(l)}(t_{n+1}) &= P^{(l)}(t_n) + h [\beta_{sp} S^{(l)}(t_n) - \beta_{ph} P^{(l)}(t_n)], \\
H^{(l)}(t_{n+1}) &= H^{(l)}(t_n) + h [\beta_{sh} S^{(l)}(t_n) + \beta_{ph} P^{(l)}(t_n)]
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where $B^{(l)}(t_n)$ is the proportion of bare soil, $G^{(l)}(t_n)$, $S^{(l)}(t_n)$, $P^{(l)}(t_n)$ and $H^{(l)}(t_n)$ are the proportions of grass (G), shrubs (S), seeders (pines, P) and resprouters (holm oaks, H) within the l -th cell at time t_n yr and $h = 1/12$ yr. The transition parameters β_{xy} indicate the transition probability from vegetation class x to vegetation class y . Note that time t_n is expressed as $t_n = nh$ where n is the number of (monthly) time steps in the simulation, varying from $n = 0$ (initial conditions) to $n = N$; for example, $n = 18$ corresponds to $t_n = 1.5$ years. Notice that bare soil undergoes transition to grass, grass to shrubs, shrubs to both seeders and resprouters, and seeders to resprouters. Without disturbances, the final outcome of the model's vegetation succession is an homogeneous cover of resprouters.

2.3 Fire Events

Fire is a key disturbance factor, significantly impacting vegetation structure by resetting cells to earlier successional stages. Fire events occur stochastically; here, we assume that the probability of fire in each cell is determined by the vegetation composition in the cell. Specifically, here we assume that (again, other choices are possible):

- **Bare soil** is assumed to be non flammable.

- **Grassland areas** are assumed to be highly flammable, making cells with dominant grass cover more susceptible to frequent fires. This high fire probability limits the development of shrub and woodland, reinforcing grassland persistence.
- **Shrubland areas** have moderate to high flammability, in some cases reducing fire frequency relative to grasslands. Here we assume shrub flammability to be slightly lower than grass flammability.
- **Seeder tree areas** are highly flammable due to characteristics of this type of trees.
- **Resprouter tree areas** are the least flammable due to dense canopy cover, which lowers fire probability and promotes woodland resilience. Cells dominated by woodland experience fewer fire events.

The probability of fire occurring in a given cell is calculated based on the vegetation type's flammability and a baseline annual fire probability f . Thus, the probability of fire occurring in a cell $F^{(l)}(t_n)$ in the time interval h between t_n and t_{n+1} is given by:

$$F^{(l)}(t_n) = hf \left[\nu_g G^{(l)}(t_n) + \nu_s S^{(l)}(t_n) + \nu_p P^{(l)}(t_n) + \nu_h H^{(l)}(t_n) \right],$$

where $0 < \nu_h < \nu_p \leq \nu_s \approx \nu_g < 1$ are the relative flammability values for resprouters, seeders, shrubs and grass respectively. The probability f can be modulated by a seasonal cycle, with higher values in summer than in winter, and/or a dependence on the soil moisture conditions, as discussed in Sect. 4.4.

Finally, another possibility is to calculate the probability of fire in a cell based only on the dominant (in the sense of fraction of area covered) vegetation type's flammability, ignoring non-dominant vegetation flammabilities.

At each timestep, and for each cell, it is determined whether that cell burns or not on the basis of its fire probability $F^{(l)}$. A fire event occurs stochastically when the ignition parameter Φ is $\Phi = 1$ and it does not occur when $\Phi = 0$. The parameter for ignition is defined by means of a Bernoulli distribution

$$\Phi \sim \text{Bernoulli}(F^{(l)}),$$

When a fire occurs, it affects vegetation composition in the cell by reducing shrub and woodland cover, converting a portion of the burned vegetation to bare soil, and depositing burned organic material in the soil. If a fire occurs in cell l at time t_n , the burned area BA in that cell is given by:

$$BA^{(l)}(t_n) = \alpha_g G^{(l)}(t_n) + \alpha_s S^{(l)}(t_n) + \alpha_p P^{(l)}(t_n) + \alpha_h H^{(l)}(t_n)$$

where $0 < \alpha_g, \alpha_s, \alpha_p, \alpha_h < 1$ represent fire severities, i.e. the proportions of grass, shrub, seeders and resprouters area cover burned by the fire, respectively.

Recalling the formulation above, the full model vegetation dynamics (including fires) from t_n to $t_{n+1} = t_n + h$ is thus given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
B^{(l)}(t_{n+1}) &= B^{(l)}(t_n) - h [\beta_{bg} B^{(l)}(t_n)] + \Phi BA^{(l)}(t_n), \\
G^{(l)}(t_{n+1}) &= G^{(l)}(t_n) + h [\beta_{bg} B^{(l)}(t_n) - \beta_{gs} G^{(l)}(t_n)] - \Phi \alpha_g G^{(l)}(t_n), \\
S^{(l)}(t_{n+1}) &= S^{(l)}(t_n) + h [\beta_{gs} G^{(l)}(t_n) \\
&\quad - \beta_{sp} S^{(l)}(t_n) - \beta_{sh} S^{(l)}(t_n)] - \Phi \alpha_s S^{(l)}(t_n), \\
P^{(l)}(t_{n+1}) &= P^{(l)}(t_n) + h [\beta_{sp} S^{(l)}(t_n) - \beta_{ph} P^{(l)}(t_n)] - \Phi \alpha_p P^{(l)}(t_n), \\
H^{(l)}(t_{n+1}) &= H^{(l)}(t_n) + h [\beta_{sh} S^{(l)}(t_n) + \beta_{ph} P^{(l)}(t_n)] - \Phi \alpha_h H^{(l)}(t_n).
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

In the time step from t_n to t_{n+1} , fire, when present ($\Phi = 1$), adds burning to the normal successional dynamics, generating bare soil and reducing vegetation cover.

2.4 Fire Propagation

The above formulation is at the level of the single cell, that is, no coupling between the dynamics in different cells is included. Coupling can occur mainly at the level of fire propagation, which is assumed to take place entirely in the time span from t_n to t_{n+1} . Two main options are envisaged in the model:

- A simple probability-based fire propagation: around each ignited cell at time step t_n (say cell j), all eight neighbouring cells are tested and instantaneously burned if their probability of burning $F^{(k)}$ is higher than a given threshold F_{thr} . For each of these newly burned cell (i.e., the cells where the fire propagated), the procedure is repeated and the cells around them are explored and possibly burned if their probability of burning is $F^{(l)}(t_n) \geq F_{thr}$. The whole procedure is repeated for a fixed number of times max_{iter} . The value of F_{thr} can be defined *a priori*, or it can be put equal to the probability of burning of the initial cell from which fire propagates, $F_{thr} = F^{(j)}(t_n)$.
- On each ignited cell at time t_n , a fire propagation model is activated and run (e.g., the model Propagator, [4]).

3 RothC Soil Carbon Model

The RothC model simulates the decomposition and turnover of soil organic carbon by dividing it into five main compartments: Decomposable Plant Material (DPM), Resistant Plant Material (RPM), Microbial Biomass (BIO), Humified Organic Matter (HUM), and Inert Organic Matter (IOM). Each compartment

decays at a specific rate influenced by environmental conditions, including temperature, moisture, and soil cover [3].

The RothC model dynamically updates each soil carbon pool on a monthly basis, decomposing material at rates modified by environmental factors. The equations for updating the values of each compartment are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{DPM}(t_{n+1}) &= \text{DPM}(t_n) - h \rho(t_n) k_{\text{dpm}} \text{DPM}(t_n) + \text{DPM}_{\text{input}}(t_n), \\
\text{RPM}(t_{n+1}) &= \text{RPM}(t_n) - h \rho(t_n) k_{\text{rpm}} \text{RPM}(t_n) + \text{RPM}_{\text{input}}(t_n), \\
\text{BIO}(t_{n+1}) &= \text{BIO}(t_n) + h \rho(t_n) [-k_{\text{bio}}(1 - \delta_{\text{BIO}}) \text{BIO}(t_n) \\
&\quad + \delta_{\text{BIO}}(k_{\text{dpm}} \text{DPM}(t_n) + k_{\text{rpm}} \text{RPM}(t_n) + k_{\text{hum}} \text{HUM}(t_n))], \\
\text{HUM}(t_{n+1}) &= \text{HUM}(t_n) + h \rho(t_n) [-k_{\text{hum}}(1 - \delta_{\text{HUM}}) \text{HUM}(t_n) \\
&\quad + \delta_{\text{HUM}}(k_{\text{dpm}} \text{DPM}(t_n) + k_{\text{rpm}} \text{RPM}(t_n) + k_{\text{bio}} \text{BIO}(t_n))].
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Here δ_{BIO} and δ_{HUM} represent partitioning factors for decomposed material entering the BIO and HUM pools, respectively; from the clay content cly we evaluate the soil texture factor as $x = 1.67(1.85 + 1.60 e^{-0.0786 \text{ cly}})$, and consequently $\delta_{\text{BIO}} = \frac{0.46}{x+1}$ and $\delta_{\text{HUM}} = \frac{1}{x+1} - \delta_{\text{BIO}}$.

The decomposition rate of each soil carbon pool is modified, through the parameter ρ , by environmental factors which are provided from the outside (data or climate model/reanalysis outputs):

- **Temperature** affects decomposition through an exponential-type response that increases decomposition rates at higher temperatures. The temperature modifier is defined as

$$\rho_{\text{temp}}(T) = \frac{47.91}{1 + \exp\left(\frac{106.06}{T+C-T^{(0)}}\right)}, \quad C = \frac{106.06}{\ln(46.91)},$$

where T is the monthly air temperature and $T^{(0)}$ is the mean annual air temperature used as a reference (computed as the average of the 12 monthly mean temperatures at the start of the simulation). By construction, $\rho_{\text{temp}}(T^{(0)}) = 1$.

- **Soil moisture** influences decomposition based on the accumulated soil moisture deficit (tsmd), with reduced decomposition under drier conditions. The maximum soil moisture deficit M and the point M_b at which respiration (i.e., microorganism activity) begins to slow are defined as

$$M = \frac{(20 + 1.3 \text{ cly} - 0.01 \text{ cly}^2) d}{23}, \quad M_b = 0.444 M.$$

The accumulated soil moisture deficit is calculated starting from the first time at which evaporation exceeds rainfall, and it is capped by the maximum soil moisture deficit M . When rainfall exceeds evaporation, the soil starts to wet up. Let $m = \text{tsmd}$; the moisture factor is

$$\rho_{\text{moisture}} = \begin{cases} 1.0 & \text{if } m < M_b, \\ 0.2 + 0.8 \frac{M - m}{M - M_b} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Note that from the definitions of ρ_{moisture} , M , M_b and m , there is a relationship between ρ_{moisture} and the Volumetric Water Content, VWC:

$$\rho_{\text{moisture}} = 0.2 + 0.8 \frac{\text{VWC} - \text{VWC}_w}{0.56 (\text{VWC}_{fc} - \text{VWC}_w)}$$

where VWC is the volume of water in a unit volume of soil, VWC_w is the value at wilting point, and VWC_{fc} is the value at field capacity. The Volumetric Water Content VWC is related to the relative soil moisture, s , by $s = \text{VWC}/\lambda$ where λ is soil porosity.

- **Soil Cover** reduces decomposition rates when vegetation is present, for example with

$$\rho_{\text{cover}}^{(\text{grass})} = 0.6, \quad \rho_{\text{cover}}^{(\text{shrub})} = 0.5, \quad \rho_{\text{cover}}^{(\text{wood})} = 0.4,$$

while bare soil does not contribute to decomposition. Here we have assumed the same soil cover factor $\rho_{\text{cover}}^{(\text{wood})}$ for all types of trees (seeders and resprouters).

Temperature and soil moisture are either provided from measured or modelled data (a typical seasonal cycle or the outcome of monthly measurements or simulations), soil moisture can also be calculated from a water balance model including precipitation and evapotranspiration.

The combined modifier of decomposition is calculated as:

$$\rho = \rho_{\text{temp}} \times \rho_{\text{moisture}} \times \rho_{\text{cover}};$$

the combined modifier adjusts the decomposition rate k of each compartment based on environmental conditions.

The total monthly carbon input from vegetation to soil ($V_{\text{input}}^{\text{TOT}}$) feeds the system, distributing carbon between the DPM and RPM compartments. This distribution is defined as follows:

$$\text{DPM}_{\text{input}}(t_n) = \gamma V_{\text{input}}^{\text{TOT}}(t_n),$$

and

$$\text{RPM}_{\text{input}}(t_n) = (1 - \gamma) V_{\text{input}}^{\text{TOT}}(t_n),$$

where $0 < \gamma < 1$ is a factor which controls the distribution of vegetation carbon inputs between the decomposable and resistant pools. Higher values of γ direct more of the vegetation input to DPM, whereas lower values direct more to RPM.

4 Integrated Soil-Vegetation Model

The integrated soil-vegetation model links vegetation dynamics with the soil carbon turnover processes from the RothC model in each cell of the grid at monthly scale. At time t_n in the l -th cell, the amount of soil carbon is distributed among the RothC compartments: $DPM^{(l)}(t_n)$, $RPM^{(l)}(t_n)$, $BIO^{(l)}(t_n)$, $HUM^{(l)}(t_n)$, $IOM^{(l)}(t_n)$.

4.1 Vegetation Influence on Decomposition Rate

Vegetation influences decomposition through a soil-cover modifier $\rho_{\text{cover}}^{(l)}(t_n)$, computed as a weighted average of cover-specific factors:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{\text{cover}}^{(l)}(t_n) = & B^{(l)}(t_n) + \rho_{\text{cover}}^{(\text{grass})} G^{(l)}(t_n) + \rho_{\text{cover}}^{(\text{shrub})} S^{(l)}(t_n) \\ & + \rho_{\text{cover}}^{(\text{wood})} \left(P^{(l)}(t_n) + H^{(l)}(t_n) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where here we use $\rho_{\text{cover}}^{(\text{grass})} = 0.8$, $\rho_{\text{cover}}^{(\text{shrub})} = 0.7$, and $\rho_{\text{cover}}^{(\text{wood})} = 0.6$ (assumed identical for seeders and resprouters).

4.2 Vegetation Influence on Soil Carbon Inputs

In each grid cell l , the vegetation input to soil carbon during the time interval from t_n to t_{n+1} , $V_{\text{TOT}}^{(l)}(t_n)$, comes from two sources: the carbon flux generated by plant metabolism and transferred to the soil through litterfall/turnover, $V_{\text{meta}}^{(l)}(t_n)$, and the carbon flux associated with fire events, $V_{\text{fire}}^{(l)}(t_n)$. Accordingly, the total carbon input to the soil is written as

$$V_{\text{TOT}}^{(l)}(t_n) = V_{\text{meta}}^{(l)}(t_n) + \Phi V_{\text{fire}}^{(l)}(t_n), \quad (6)$$

where $V_{\text{meta}}^{(l)}$ denotes the *effective* (climate-limited) metabolic input and $V_{\text{fire}}^{(l)}$ the fraction of fire-affected carbon that is actually deposited into the soil.

In the model, we define the monthly carbon inputs from vegetation metabolism in the time interval from t_n to t_{n+1} as a function of the proportions of grassland (G), shrubland (S), and woodland (W) in each cell:

$$V_{\text{meta},0}^{(l)}(t_n) = h \left[\xi_g \mu_g G^{(l)}(t_n) + \xi_s \mu_s S^{(l)}(t_n) + \xi_p \mu_p P^{(l)}(t_n) + \xi_h \mu_h H^{(l)}(t_n) \right],$$

where $G^{(l)}(t_n)$, $S^{(l)}(t_n)$, $P^{(l)}(t_n)$ and $H^{(l)}(t_n)$ are the proportions of grassland, shrubland, seeders and resprouters, respectively, in the l -th cell at time t_n . Here, $\xi_g \mu_g$, $\xi_s \mu_s$, $\xi_p \mu_p$ and $\xi_h \mu_h$ are constants representing the factors that convert vegetation area cover into carbon amount for grassland, shrubland, seeders and resprouters, respectively. Each of these products includes two different parameters: ξ , that represents the conversion from fraction of covered area to carbon content of the vegetation biomass (i.e., it is in mass/surface), and μ , which represents the carbon stored in the soil by metabolism per unit carbon in the plant

and per year (i.e., mass/mass/time). For simplicity, here we assume an average value of the parameters ξ_g , ξ_s , ξ_p and ξ_h , that is, we do not take into account the age and size structure of the vegetation classes.

Hydrologically limited metabolic inputs. To increase realism in the coupled vegetation–soil framework, we explicitly account for the fact that under drought conditions vegetation productivity and turnover (and thus litter inputs) are typically reduced. In the above expression of $V_{\text{meta},0}^{(l)}$, however, the vegetation-derived input provided to the soil module does not respond to moisture stress, whereas decomposition is already moisture-limited through the RothC soil-moisture modifier. As a result, drought can decrease decomposition while leaving inputs unchanged, which would bias SOC dynamics. To ensure a consistent coupling, we make the metabolic inputs to depend on drought by scaling them with a water-stress factor $f_W(\rho_{\text{moisture}}^{(l)})$:

$$V_{\text{meta}}^{(l)}(t_n) = V_{\text{meta},0}^{(l)}(t_n) f_W(\rho_{\text{moisture}}^{(l)}(t_n)), \quad 0 \leq f_W \leq 1. \quad (7)$$

In the present implementation, we adopt the normalization between $[0, 1]$ of $\rho_{\text{moisture}}^{(l)}$:

$$f_W(\rho_{\text{moisture}}^{(l)}) = \frac{\rho_{\text{moisture}}^{(l)} - 0.2}{0.8} \quad (8)$$

so that vegetation-derived inputs decrease proportionally with moisture limitation. In this approach, the value of $V_{\text{meta}}^{(l)}$ is an upper limit to the carbon input to the soil when soil moisture is at field capacity.

Deposition efficiency of fire-affected carbon. In case a fire occurs between time t_n and t_{n+1} , it is necessary to add the monthly carbon input from burned vegetation. This is modeled as a function of the fractions of grassland (G), shrubland (S), seeders (P) and resprouters (H) in each cell:

$$V_{\text{fire},0}^{(l)}(t_n) = \xi_g \alpha_g G^{(l)}(t_n) + \xi_s \alpha_s S^{(l)}(t_n) + \xi_p \alpha_p P^{(l)}(t_n) + \xi_h \alpha_h H^{(l)}(t_n),$$

where the coefficients are given by the product of the fraction of area burned for that specific vegetation type (fire severity), α , and the conversion from the fraction of area to vegetation carbon content, ξ . However, not all carbon affected by fire is transferred to the soil: a large fraction is emitted rapidly to the atmosphere (CO_2 , CO , aerosols), while only a fraction is deposited as residues and pyrogenic material. We therefore introduce a deposition efficiency $0 \leq \eta_{\text{dep}} \leq 1$ such that

$$V_{\text{fire}}^{(l)}(t_n) = \eta_{\text{dep}} V_{\text{fire},0}^{(l)}(t_n) \quad (9)$$

while the quantity

$$(1 - \eta_{\text{dep}}) V_{\text{fire},0}^{(l)} \quad (10)$$

is emitted to the atmosphere.

Partitioning post-fire inputs into labile vs. inert fractions. As seen above, only the non-volatilized fraction of fire-affected carbon contributes to soil inputs. In the model this is represented by the deposited flux $V_{\text{fire}}^{(l)}$, obtained by applying the deposition efficiency η_{dep} (Eq. (10)). In principle, the soil-deposited post-fire input contains both (i) a relatively labile residue component and (ii) a pyrogenic (char/black carbon) component that is substantially more recalcitrant than the labile fraction. To avoid treating all post-fire inputs as readily decomposable carbon, the model allows to partition the deposited flux as

$$V_{\text{fire}}^{(l)}(t_n) = V_{\text{char}}^{(l)}(t_n) + V_{\text{res}}^{(l)}(t_n), \quad (11)$$

where $V_{\text{char}}^{(l)}$ denotes the inert pyrogenic fraction and $V_{\text{res}}^{(l)}$ the labile residual fraction of the *deposited* (i.e. non-volatilized) fire carbon. Using a constant char fraction $0 \leq \alpha_{\text{char}} \leq 1$, the model allows to define

$$V_{\text{char}}^{(l)} = \omega_{\text{char}} V_{\text{fire}}^{(l)}, \quad V_{\text{res}}^{(l)} = (1 - \omega_{\text{char}}) V_{\text{fire}}^{(l)}. \quad (12)$$

In terms of RothC pool allocation, the model routes the labile deposited residues to the RPM pool, while the pyrogenic fraction is transferred to the inert pool (IOM):

$$\text{Input}_{\text{RPM}}^{(l)} \leftarrow \text{Input}_{\text{RPM}}^{(l)} + \Phi V_{\text{res}}^{(l)}, \quad \text{Input}_{\text{IOM}}^{(l)} \leftarrow \text{Input}_{\text{IOM}}^{(l)} + \Phi V_{\text{char}}^{(l)}. \quad (13)$$

For simplicity, here we use $\omega_{\text{char}} = 0$ so all the non-volatilized carbon is assumed to be labile and feed the RPM compartment. In fact, since the inert fraction is generally not usable on the time scales considered in the simulations, one can take into account the loss of carbon to the inert fraction by simply increasing the amount of carbon that is volatilized, thus including in this fraction the sum of the truly volatilized carbon and the carbon going to the inert pool.

The whole formulation presented here links vegetation dynamics with soil carbon inputs by adjusting the carbon input rates based on the proportions of each vegetation type in a cell. As vegetation composition changes over time due to succession or fire events, the inputs to the soil carbon pools are dynamically adjusted, reflecting the influence of vegetation structure on soil carbon dynamics.

SOC loss due to burning. In addition to carbon deposition by biomass burning, fires also burn part of the organic carbon in the soil (SOC). That is, if a fire occurs between t_n and t_{n+1} , a fraction σ of the total SOC is burned. The burned fraction is equally distributed among the components of the SOC, i.e., in a fire event, we have that all organic soil carbon components are multiplied by a factor $1 - \sigma$.

In this case, the equations for soil carbon (4) become

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{DPM}(t_{n+1}) &= \text{DPM}(t_n) - h \rho(t_n) k_{\text{dpm}} \text{DPM}(t_n) + \text{DPM}_{\text{input}}(t_n) - \Phi \sigma \text{DPM}(t_n), \\
\text{RPM}(t_{n+1}) &= \text{RPM}(t_n) - h \rho(t_n) k_{\text{rpm}} \text{RPM}(t_n) + \text{RPM}_{\text{input}}(t_n) - \Phi \sigma \text{RPM}(t_n), \\
\text{BIO}(t_{n+1}) &= \text{BIO}(t_n) + h \rho(t_n) [-k_{\text{bio}}(1 - \delta_{\text{BIO}}) \text{BIO}(t_n) \\
&\quad + \delta_{\text{BIO}} (k_{\text{dpm}} \text{DPM}(t_n) + k_{\text{rpm}} \text{RPM}(t_n) + k_{\text{hum}} \text{HUM}(t_n))] - \Phi \sigma \text{BIO}(t_n), \\
\text{HUM}(t_{n+1}) &= \text{HUM}(t_n) + h \rho(t_n) [-k_{\text{hum}}(1 - \delta_{\text{HUM}}) \text{HUM}(t_n) \\
&\quad + \delta_{\text{HUM}} (k_{\text{dpm}} \text{DPM}(t_n) + k_{\text{rpm}} \text{RPM}(t_n) + k_{\text{bio}} \text{BIO}(t_n))] - \Phi \sigma \text{HUM}(t_n).
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

4.3 Impact of Soil Carbon on Vegetation Dynamics

Soil organic carbon pools, especially the stable BIO and HUM compartments, play a role in determining vegetation resilience. Here, high levels of stable soil organic matter are assumed to enhance nutrient availability, promoting vegetation growth and accelerating succession from grassland to shrubland and woodland.

In the vegetation succession model, the values of the transition parameters in the succession, β , are made functions of the amount of soil carbon in the BIO and HUM pools, which are taken to be a proxy of the amount of nutrients in the soil. Specifically, we make β a monotonously growing function of the relative importance of the BIO and HUM pools in the total carbon content of the soil in the cell, that is, of

$$C^{(l)}(t_n) = [\text{BIO}(t_n) + \text{HUM}(t_n)] / \text{SOC}(t_n),$$

where $\text{SOC}^{(l)}(t_n)$ denotes the total carbon in the soil is given by

$$\text{SOC}^{(l)}(t_n) = \text{DPM}^{(l)}(t_n) + \text{RPM}^{(l)}(t_n) + \text{BIO}^{(l)}(t_n) + \text{HUM}^{(l)}(t_n).$$

In the approach adopted here, the dependence of β on C is modeled as a linear dependence on C . A simple choice is to write

$$\beta = \beta_0 \left[1 + \kappa C^{(l)}(t_n) \right],$$

where κ is a constant that determines how the transition rates β are increased by the availability of carbon and nutrients. In this case, the values of β_0 indicate the base transition rates, when microbial Biomass (BIO) and Humified Organic Matter (HUM) are low. Other choices are possible and they can be implemented in the model.

4.4 Effect of soil moisture

The decomposition rates in the soil carbon model depend on soil temperature and moisture. Such environmental parameters are assumed to be an external input from either modeled or tabulated conditions or direct measurements. In particular, soil moisture can be obtained either by direct measurements or by a water balance between precipitation and evapotranspiration (as computed from temperature).

Since grasslands are favoured in drier conditions, the model can make the succession transition rates from grass to shrubs and shrubs to trees dependent upon soil moisture. One option is to have a linear dependence on soil moisture. The full expressions for the β 's thus become:

$$\begin{aligned}\beta_{bg} &= \beta_{bg,0} \left[1 + \kappa C^{(l)}(t_n) \right] , \\ \beta_{gs} &= \beta_{gs,0} \left[1 + \kappa C^{(l)}(t_n) \right] \varepsilon \rho_{\text{moisture}}^{(l)}(t_n) , \\ \beta_{sp} &= \beta_{sp,0} \left[1 + \kappa C^{(l)}(t_n) \right] \varepsilon \rho_{\text{moisture}}^{(l)}(t_n) , \\ \beta_{sh} &= \beta_{sh,0} \left[1 + \kappa C^{(l)}(t_n) \right] \varepsilon \rho_{\text{moisture}}^{(l)}(t_n) , \\ \beta_{ph} &= \beta_{ph,0} \left[1 + \kappa C^{(l)}(t_n) \right] \varepsilon \rho_{\text{moisture}}^{(l)}(t_n) ,\end{aligned}$$

where ε weights how strongly the transition rates β for grass-to-shrub, shrub-to-seeders, shrub-to-resprouters and seeders-to-resprouters depend on soil moisture.

A second way soil moisture enters the integrated vegetation-fire-carbon model is through its effect on the base fire probability. Soil moisture is taken as a proxy of fuel moisture; the drier is the soil, the higher is the baseline probability of fire. Here we use ρ_{moisture} to represent soil moisture, which goes from 0.2 (soil moisture at the wilting point) to 1 (soil moisture at the soil field capacity). In particular, f can be written as a linear dependence on ρ_{moisture} , such as, for example

$$f = f_0 (1 - \rho_{\text{moisture}})$$

where f_0 is the baseline probability which can further depend on seasonality. Since $0.2 \leq \rho_{\text{moisture}} \leq 1$, f in the formula above varies between 0 (for moist soil) and $0.8 f_0$ (for dry soil).

This probability is then modulated by the type of vegetation present in the cell, and it is larger for grass cover than for shrubs and trees.

4.5 System-level dynamics

At system level, the fraction of area covered by bare soil, grassland, shrubland, and woodland, $B^{(sys)}(t_n)$, $G^{(sys)}(t_n)$, $S^{(sys)}(t_n)$, $P^{(sys)}(t_n)$ and $H^{(sys)}(t_n)$ at

time t_n is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 B^{(sys)}(t_n) &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{l=1}^N B^{(l)}(t_n), & G^{(sys)}(t_n) &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{l=1}^N G^{(l)}(t_n), \\
 S^{(sys)}(t_n) &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{l=1}^N S^{(l)}(t_n), & P^{(sys)}(t_n) &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{l=1}^N P^{(l)}(t_n), \\
 H^{(sys)}(t_n) &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{l=1}^N H^{(l)}(t_n)
 \end{aligned}$$

At system level, the total soil carbon content $SOC^{(sys)}(t)$ is defined as

$$SOC^{(sys)}(t_n) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{l=1}^N SOC^{(l)}(t_n).$$

5 Dynamic Feedbacks Between Vegetation and Soil Carbon

The integration of the vegetation model and the RothC soil carbon model allows for the emergence of complex feedback loops between vegetation structure, soil carbon dynamics, and fire disturbances. These feedbacks create conditions that reinforce certain vegetation states and influence carbon cycling within the ecosystem. Here, we describe the primary feedback loops that arise from the model's structure and dynamics.

5.1 Grassland-Fire Feedback Loop

Grasslands are characterized by relatively high flammability and low biomass, and promote frequent fire disturbances. Each fire reduces shrub and woodland cover, resetting successional stages. Grass biomass per unit area can be lower than that of shrubs and trees, but grass stores more carbon per unit biomass than trees and shrubs.

5.2 Shrubland-Soil Carbon Accumulation

In cells with intermediate vegetation dominated by shrubland, the feedback between soil carbon and vegetation dynamics creates conditions that can support gradual succession towards woodland. Shrublands have significant flammability and soil cover factor (0.7).

The moderate decomposition rate under shrubland cover promotes the buildup of soil organic carbon over time, which improves soil fertility. As BIO and HUM levels increase, they support further vegetation succession by enhancing nutrient availability. This accumulation of stable organic matter creates a positive

feedback loop that favors the progression from shrubland to woodland in areas with low fire frequency. However, this balance is sensitive to fire disturbances, and shrublands can revert to grassland if fire frequency increases.

5.3 Woodland-Resilience Feedback

Woodland areas represent the most stable state in this model, characterized by low flammability, dense canopy cover, and slow decomposition rates due to a soil cover factor of 0.6.

The dense canopy of woodland vegetation reduces soil exposure and limits the likelihood of fire, decreasing disturbance frequency in woodland-dominated cells. This low disturbance rate further supports the resilience of woodland areas, allowing them to persist even in the presence of moderate disturbances. The reduced fire risk creates a self-sustaining feedback loop that makes woodland-dominated cells resistant to shifts toward grassland or shrubland states.

5.4 Soil Carbon as a Driver of Post-Fire Vegetation Recovery

Soil organic carbon pools, particularly BIO and HUM, play a critical role in determining how quickly vegetation can recover following a fire event. In cells with high levels of BIO and HUM, nutrient availability is sufficient to accelerate regrowth and succession, allowing these areas to recover from fire disturbances more quickly. This results in shorter recovery times and promotes the re-establishment of shrub or woodland cover.

In contrast, cells with low levels of BIO and HUM experience slower vegetation recovery after a fire, often resulting in the establishment of grassland due to insufficient nutrients for succession. Over time, this difference in post-fire recovery creates spatial heterogeneity within the ecosystem, with some areas resilient to fire and others more prone to persistent grassland cover. The interaction between soil carbon content and vegetation recovery enhances the diversity of stable states within the ecosystem, promoting a mosaic of grassland, shrubland, and woodland patches.

6 Conclusion

By linking vegetation dynamics, fires and soil carbon cycling, this model captures the complex interactions between vegetation structure, fire disturbances, and soil carbon turnover. The model provides insight into feedback mechanisms that reinforce grassland or woodland dominance and highlights the role of soil organic carbon in stabilizing vegetation against disturbances. This model contributes to our understanding of ecosystem resilience and the role of soil carbon in fire-prone landscapes and to understanding the interactions between fires and Critical Zone dynamics.

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Table 1: Example values of the Vegetation - Fire - Soil Carbon model parameters to be used in the simulations.

Parameter	Example Value	Description
GENERAL		
cellsize	0.04	Cell size [ha] - equivalent to 400 m ²
gridsize	90000	Grid dimensions (e.g., 300x300 cells)
h	1/12	Simulation timestep in years
numbersteps	1000	Total simulation time in years
VEGETATION SUCCESSION		
$\beta_{0,bg}$	0.5	Base annual succession rate for bare soil-to-grass (1/yr)
$\beta_{0,gs}$	0.3	Base annual succession rate for grass-to-shrub (1/yr)
$\beta_{0,sp}$	0.2	Base annual succession rate for shrub-to-seeders (1/yr)
$\beta_{0,sh}$	0.1	Base annual succession rate for shrub-to-resprouters (1/yr)
$\beta_{0,ph}$	0.05	Base annual succession rate for seeders-to-resprouters (1/yr)
ϵ	1	Soil-moisture-related decrease parameter of the transition rates
κ	1	Carbon-related increase parameter of the transition rates β
FIRE DYNAMICS		
f_0	0.2	Annual dry-soil base fire probability factor in a cell [1/yr]
ζ	0.2	Correction factor to dry-soil base fire probability due to soil moisture
ν_g	0.6	Flammability of grass
ν_s	0.5	Flammability of shrub
ν_p	0.4	Flammability of seeders
ν_h	0.2	Flammability of resprouters
α_g	1	Fire severity for grassland
α_s	0.6	Fire severity for shrubland
α_p	0.6	Fire severity for seeders
α_h	0.3	Fire severity for resprouters
F_{thr}	0.015	Fixed probability threshold for fire propagation
max_{iter}	10	Number of concentric cell areas for checking fire propagation
CARBON DYNAMICS		
cly	30.0	Soil clay content as a percentage
d	23	Soil depth in cm
k_{DPM}	10	Decay rate for Decomposable Plant Material (DPM) [1/yr]
k_{RPM}	0.3	Decay rate for Resistant Plant Material (RPM) [1/yr]
k_{BIO}	0.66	Decay rate for Microbial Biomass (BIO) [1/yr]
k_{HUM}	0.02	Decay rate for Humified Organic Matter (HUM) [1/yr]
M	50.0	Maximum soil moisture deficit (absolute value) in mm
M_b	22.2	Bacteria-related soil moisture deficit (absolute value) in mm
δ_{BIO}	0.1059	BIO pool partitioning factor
δ_{HUM}	0.1244	HUM pool partitioning factor
γ	0.59	Partitioning factor for vegetation inputs
ξ_g	20	Vegetation carbon content per unit area [ton/ha] - grass
ξ_s	30	Vegetation carbon content per unit area [ton/ha] - shrubs
ξ_p	50	Vegetation carbon content per unit area [ton/ha] - seeders
ξ_h	50	Vegetation carbon content per unit area [ton/ha] - resprouters
μ_g	0.05	Fraction of carbon stored per year [ton/ton/yr] - grass
μ_s	0.05	Fraction of carbon stored per year [ton/ton/yr] [ton/ton/yr] - shrubs
μ_p	0.03	Fraction of carbon stored per year [ton/ton/yr] [ton/ton/yr] - seeders
μ_h	0.03	Fraction of carbon stored per year [ton/ton/yr] [ton/ton/yr] - resprouters
η_{dep}	0.40	Fraction of non-volatilized plant carbon stored in soil by fire
ω_{char}	0.0	Fraction of deposited carbon stored in the inert pool by fire
σ	0.20	Fraction of soil organic carbon (SOC) burned by a fire event
$\rho_{cover}^{(grass)}$	0.6	Soil cover factor for grassland
$\rho_{cover}^{(shrub)}$	0.5	Soil cover factor for shrubland
$\rho_{cover}^{(wood)}$	0.4	Soil cover factor for trees (seeders and resprouters)